

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF FORMATION OF NATIONAL VALUES IN THE PROCESS OF EDUCATING YOUNG PEOPLE

Turemuratova Aziza Begibaevna

Assistant, Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, Karakalpak State University
named after Berdakh, Republic of Karakalpakstan:

Qaypnazarova Zubayda Qongratbay qizi

A student of applied psychology at Karakalpak State University:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10017449>

Abstract: In the pedagogical and psychological training of young people in the higher education system, it is necessary to convey to them our national values, history, culture and the main factors in the formation of our worldview. I believe that the contribution of educational institutions in raising our young people to be loyal children to the motherland is huge. Nowadays, many opportunities and conditions have been created for young people. Our young people grow up to become perfect people, and their chances to serve their people are very high.

Keywords: National value, historical memory, future generation, pedagogical and psychological factors, cultured and enlightened person.

Introduction

Today, national values and interethnic harmony are being preserved in our country there are all necessary conditions for further strengthening the atmosphere of religious tolerance is being created. The participation of the young generation in the life of a comprehensively developing society in getting them interested in the national values and spirituality of the Uzbek people it is important for everyone to introduce historical memories as well as universal human values is one of the tasks. Therefore, national and universal values are included in the educational content assimilation, mutual understanding of representatives of different nationalities, cooperation and cultural enables them to enjoy spiritual wealth. Education as a result of this approach system, young people absorb the cultural wealth of the Uzbek people. Education for this purpose the values of Uzbek and world nations are embedded in its content. National values should appear as a component of individual culture. First of all, let's talk about personal culture in the formation of the worldview of young people, personal culture means the thoughts of a certain person, a complex of material and spiritual wealth created by his mind and hands during his life actions related to humaneness and compliance with moral and educational

requirements includes the concept. The psychological culture of a person is the creative ideas he created, national culture, spiritual and moral it is manifested in adherence to values. The psychological culture of a person is his spiritual upbringing is the criterion that determines the level. Signs of personal psychological culture are the following spiritual and moral qualities, human relations are also expressed by the acquisition of qualities: faithful, conscientious, faithful and being pious, polite and disciplined, well-educated, knowledgeable, intelligent, studying and not being late for work and striving to enrich the worldview, keeping promises, not harming people, doing good doing and not thanking him, respecting elders and honoring the younger, old people, women and respect for children, kindness, warmth, humility, not to call others nicknames, not to laugh at people's shortcomings, not to make fun of them, not to discriminate against the weak, not to interfere with the work and rest of the people around them, hospitality, paying attention to one's inner and outer world, observing speech culture, preservation of public property, physical and spiritual purity, etc. Personal culture unites him with the team, gives him the opportunity to make many friends. Enriching spiritual and moral qualities, self-improvement ability to educate, control and manage, self-critical approach, worldview should expand and raise its cultural level. National values are important and fundamental to a nation's unique history and culture refers to principles, beliefs and ideals. These values are the behavior of citizens, shapes attitudes and aspirations. They often shaped the nation over time reflects historical, cultural, religious and philosophical influences. National values are an important and serious aspect and feature for a nation. A nation without its own national values has no culture. The nation is the owner of national values. National values - national history, unity of lifestyle, its future, generations, social strata, nationality, consciousness, language, spirituality and culture is inextricably linked with In terms of pedagogical and psychological factors in education, all the riches of the culture of the Uzbek people, the national heritage of our ancestors it is necessary to express the views of the peoples living in Uzbekistan on tolerance, lifestyle, traditions, customs, norms of social behavior and spiritual values. Education the main place in its content is the knowledge of the spiritual life of the Uzbek people, the national way of life, must acquire concepts and information. In particular, the national education of the Uzbek people a special place for information that shows cultural, social, economic and territorial identity should be separated. National values can vary significantly from one country to another. One of the main national values is freedom.

Freedom - political freedom, personal freedom, it covers various aspects such as freedom of speech and belief. Citizens often make decisions has the right to participate in processes and use certain rights and protections is the basis of democratic societies. National values are often reflected in a country's laws, policies, educational programs, reflected in cultural expressions and public activities. Understanding national values is essential for politicians, leaders and citizens. Because they determine the actions and priorities of the nation. They decide provides a basis for policy formulation and management. National values and national identity it also plays an important role in forming and educating citizens' sense of belonging. Pedagogical foundations of national values are important for a nation or society educational principles used in inculcating and promoting cherished values and practices are understood. These values are often patriotism, respect for authority, cultural heritage, social includes concepts such as solidarity and ethical behavior. National in different countries and cultures, the pedagogical approach to teaching values is different, but it usually involves a combination of formal education, informal socialization and cultural transmission takes. All the riches of the culture of the Uzbek people, the national heritage of our ancestors in the content of education tolerance, views on the lifestyle and traditions of the peoples living in Uzbekistan, traditions, norms of social behavior and spiritual values should be reflected. Education the main place in its content is the knowledge of the spiritual life of the Uzbek people, the national way of life, must acquire concepts and information. In particular, the national education of the Uzbek people a special place for information that shows cultural, social, economic and territorial identity should be separated. One of the important aspects of the pedagogical and psychological foundations of national values is the personality the role of formal education in the formation of values is of great importance. Higher education institutions educational programs and training plays a crucial role in conveying national values by incorporating national values into its materials. This Based in Pedagogy, Psychology, Education or Civics or Social Studies can be done through subject questionnaires. Students here they will have the opportunity to get acquainted with the history, political system and cultural heritage of their country. Studying these subjects through this, the youth will gain knowledge about their nation and their identity and values develop a sense of belonging. Apart from formal education, informal socialization is also important in the formation of national values plays an important role. Informal socialization refers to family members, peers, and society values, beliefs and interactions with members and the media

the process of acquiring behavior is understood. The family is often the main agent of socialization is considered because parents transmit their values and beliefs to children in everyday communication and behavior modeling. Peers and national values plays a role in the formation, because the attitude and behavior of friends of young people they learn. Cultural transmission is another important aspect of the pedagogical foundations of national values culture is the general beliefs, customs and traditions that characterize a certain group or society. National tradition is our national history, our values. National values are often specific to a country's culture passed down from generation to generation through various means such as rituals, festivals and cultural events. For example, national holidays or festivals are an opportunity for individuals to learn national values can serve as an opportunity for strengthening. Historical events also form the pedagogical basis of national values possible. For example, countries that have experienced wars or conflicts, courage, sacrifice and can emphasize values such as unity. On the other hand, to the history of colonialism or oppression countries that have priority to values such as independence, equality and social justice can give cultural diversity is another influence on the pedagogical basis of national values factor. In multicultural societies, it is often national with respect for cultural diversity there is a need to balance the promotion of values. In short, the pedagogical foundations of national values are for the nation or society educational principles used in inculcating and promoting values that are considered important and practices. Pedagogical approach in different countries and cultures vary, but generally include national values in the curriculum, family and peer interaction socialization of youth through relationships and values through cultural practices includes delivery. Political ideologies, social norms, historical events and cultural factors such as diversity affect the pedagogical basis of national values.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we would like to say that we are all equally responsible for the development of young people in the future. Our youth is the tomorrow of our country. The way we educate and educate the youth, the development of our country will increase even more. Educating our young people to be educated, intelligent and polite is the main priority in shaping their worldview. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, our young people are currently showing good results in many fields.

References:

1. Begibaevna T. A. USE OF EDUCATIONAL TRADITIONS OF FOLK PEDAGOGY IN FORMING YOUTH WORLD VIEW //EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD). – 2023. – Т. 8. – №. 6. – С. 266-268.
2. Turemuratova A., Ostonakulov I. USING PROVERBS AS A WAY OF FOLK PEDAGOGY TO IMPROVE THE KNOWLEDGE OF YOUTH //International Journal of Intellectual Cultural Heritage. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 17-20.
3. Turemuratova, A. (2023). EDUCATIONAL TRADITIONS IN THE FORMATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE'S WORLD VIEW IN FOLK PEDAGOGY.
4. Turemuratova A. USE OF EDUCATIONAL TRADITIONS OF FOLK PEDAGOGY IN FORMING YOUTH WORLD VIEW //" Мировая наука"№ 6 (75) 2023 science-j. com. – 2023.
5. Turemuratova, A., & Temirbekov, B. (2022). Mustahkam oilani shakllantirishda yoshlarda naql-maqollardan foydalanishning tarbiyaviy-psixologik ahamiyati.
6. Turemuratova, A. (2021). Har bir xalqning o'z qadriyati bor.
7. Turemuratova, A. . (2022). USING PROVERBS AS A WAY OF FOLK PEDAGOGY TO IMPROVE THE KNOWLEDGE OF YOUTH. International Journal of Intellectual Cultural Heritage, 2(6), 60–63. Retrieved from <http://ihm.iscience.uz/index.php/ijich/article/view/196>
8. Turemuratova, A., & Asamatdinova, J. (2021). Talabalar qadriyatqa bag'darlang'anliqti rivajlantiruwda auditoriyadan tis shinig'iwlaridin' roli.
9. Turemuratova A. TRADITIONS OF FORMING THE SPIRITUAL AND MORAL WORLDVIEW OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN PEDAGOGY //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 7. – С. 225-229.
10. Begibaevna, Turemuratova Aziza. "EDUCATIONAL TRADITIONS IN THE FORMATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE'S WORLD VIEW IN FOLK PEDAGOGY." Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities 11.5 (2023): 1292-1295.
11. Туремуратова А. Б. ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ВОСПИТАТЕЛЬНЫХ ТРАДИЦИЙ НАРОДНОЙ ПЕДАГОГИКИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ МИРОВОЗЗРЕНИЯ МОЛОДЕЖИ //Мировая наука. – 2023. – №. 6 (75). – С. 125-129.
12. Jumamuratov R. E., Kaipbergenov A. T. TEACHING CHEMISTRY IN HIGH SCHOOLS //Экономика и социум. – 2023. – №. 8 (111). – С. 101-107.
13. Jumamuratov R. E., Kaipbergenov A. T. STAGES OF PEDAGOGICAL ANALYSIS OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL MODELS IN THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN //Экономика и социум. – 2023. – №. 8 (111). – С. 96-100.

14. Jumamuratov R., Kaipbergenov A. APPLICATION OF INFORMATION AND COMPUTER TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING CHEMISTRY //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 7. – С. 21-26.
15. Kaipbergenov A. The methodology of teaching chemistry based on the use of computer programs //Scienceweb academic papers collection. – 2019.
16. Bekturganova Z. МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНОЙ РАБОТЕ УЧАЩИХСЯ НА УРОКЕ ХИМИИ //Scienceweb academic papers collection. – 2017.
17. Jumamuratov R., Aynazarova S., Embergenova U. KIMYONI O'QITISH VOSITALARI TIZIMI VA UNING DIDAKTIK IMKONIYATLARINI O'RGANISH //Интернаука. – 2021. – №. 16-4. – С. 90-92.
18. Бектурганова З. К., Жумамуратов Р. Е., Бектилеуова Г. Б. Использование новых информационных технологий в обучении химии //современное экологическое состояние природной среды и научно-практические аспекты рационального природопользования. – 2017. – С. 2105-2107.
19. Бектурганова З. К., Жумамуратов Р. Е. МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНОЙ РАБОТЕ УЧАЩИХСЯ НА УРОКЕ ХИМИИ //СОВРЕМЕННОЕ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ПРИРОДНОЙ СРЕДЫ И НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ РАЦИОНАЛЬНОГО ПРИРОДОПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ. – 2017. – С. 2103-2105.
20. Abdirazakov, I., & Jumamuratov, R. (2022). МАКТАВДА КИМYO FANINI O'QITISHDA КОМПYУТЕР МОДЕЛЛАРИНИ QO'LLASH.

